

**Is nudging effective to reduce meat consumption in food service?
A pre-registered protocol of a systematic review and meta-analysis of field intervention studies**

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1. Introduction and Rationale

A reduction of meat consumption would have several benefits for the environment and human health (Clark et al., 2019). It is widely acknowledged that future sustainable and healthy diets should be predominantly plant-based. However, meat takes a central part in Western diets and changing consumer behavior towards a more plant-based life-style faces many obstacles (SAPEA, 2023).

Dual process theories of human decision making conceptual two alternative modes (automatic/habitual versus reflective/rational): The automatic or habitual mode involves little active decision-making, information is processed automatically and heuristically. In the reflective/rational mode, information is processed in a reflected way and choice options are carefully considered (Evans, 2008). Most daily food choices are made habitually and are a result of the automatic system. Accordingly, political measures that address the reflective, rational system, for example educating and informing people about the benefits of meat reduction to change attitudes and intentions, have not been so effective to change consumer behavior in the past (SAPEA, 2023). Indeed, a recent study shows that intentions to reduce meat consumption do often not transform into actual behavior for a large part of the population (Schäufele-Elbers & Janssen, 2023).

There is much more potential to change factors of the physical, social or psychological environment in which food choices take place. This approach is named choice architecture intervention and became famous as the concept of “nudging”. Nudging is a tool that aims to change behavior (rather than attitudes and beliefs) towards personally and socially favorite decisions through altering the choice architecture without changing economic incentives or the freedom of choice (Thaler & Sunstein, 2009; Thaler et al., 2013). A recent meta-analysis on nudging in different behavioral domains suggests that the food sector is particularly perceptive to nudges (Mertens et al., 2022): while the average ou of nudging interventions across all behavioral dimensions was just within the lower range (Cohen’s $d=0.43$), it was of medium size in the food domain (Cohen’s $d=0.65$). A meta-analysis examining the effectiveness of healthy eating nudges indicated that the average effect size was relatively modest (Cohen's $d = 0.23$). However, it is noteworthy that behaviorally-oriented nudges showed a more promising effect size (Cohen's $d = 0.39$) (Cadario & Chandon, 2020). These results instils optimism regarding the effectiveness of similar strategies in steering individuals away from meat and towards plant-based choices.

Meat is omnipresent in food service environments, typically occupying prominent positions, while meat-free dishes often receive limited visibility. Furthermore, the labelling or framing of vegetarian or vegan options is often unappealing, while meat is considered the social norm or default choice (SAPEA, 2023). Given the fact that consumers behave in a meat supporting environment, much potential is given to nudging interventions that modify the choice architecture, i.e. the design of the environment in which

consumers make decisions. In the literature, this choice environment is divided into three broad categories: decision information, decision structure and decision assistance and several associated nudging techniques (Münscher et al., 2016) (see table 1). The category ‘decision information’ includes different techniques such as framing and labelling that provide decision-relevant information to consumers. For meat reduction in food service, climate labels or information on the taste and healthiness can be assigned to this category. However, there is an ongoing debate regarding whether these techniques can be considered pure nudges or if they fall under conventional information interventions that target the reflective or rational decision-making system (Kosters & van der Heijden, 2015). Following the arguments put forth by Slapø and Karevold (2019) and Ölander and Thøgersen (2014), the addition of information at the moment of choice, such as simple labels (e.g. single green or red label; traffic light) or descriptions of menu items that are very easy to process (e.g. delicious or tasty) can be classified as nudges.

Within the category of ‘decision structure’ fall all techniques that alter the way options are arranged and the decision making format, for example the availability of vegetarian or vegan options, the variety or arrangement of options, the default option, or the effort required for selecting an option. The third category ‘decision assistance’ covers interventions that foster the transition of intentions into behavior such as reminders or commitment (Münscher et al., 2016). This classification system was chosen because it is very comprehensive and covers all nudging categories relevant for meat reduction in food service. Moreover, it has been already used by a former meta-analysis on nudging (Mertens et al., 2022).

Table 1: Nudging categories and nudging techniques

Category	Technique	Application for meat reduction in food service
A. Decision information	A.1 Translate information	Different menu-names for meat-free dishes (Rosenfeld et al., 2022)
	A.2 Make information visible	Simple eco/sustainability labels for example traffic light (Lohmann et al., 2022; Slapø & Karevold, 2019), images from 0 to 5 green leaves (Piester et al., 2020) Description of dishes as tasty or healthy (e.g. healthy choice, tasty choice) (Piester et al., 2020; Turnwald & Crum, 2019)
	A.3 Provide social reference points	Information about the eating behavior of others (Çoker et al., 2022) Dish of the Day Nudge (Saulais et al., 2019)
B. Decision structure	B.1 Change choice defaults	Vegetarian lunch default (Hansen et al., 2021)
	B.2 Change option-related effort	Change the convenience of ordering a meat/vegetarian dish (Gravert & Kurz, 2017)
	B.3 Change range or composition of options	Top menu position (Langen et al., 2022) Change the menu order (Kurz, 2018)
	B.4 Change option consequences	No study assignable so far
C. Decision assistance	C.1 Provide reminders	No study assignable so far
	C.2 Facilitate commitment	No study assignable so far

Source: Adapted from Münscher et al. (2016)

Field experiment and framed field experiments are well-suited for testing nudging interventions in the food service sector due to their ability to capture real consumer choices, resulting in high external validity of the data collected. Online choice experiments on nudging do not capture actual consumption outcomes. Furthermore, actual choice data is less susceptible to social desirability bias compared to self-reported data. In surveys, consumers may feel a social pressure to present themselves as more environmentally conscious or health-conscious than they really are, potentially overestimating their actual meat reduction efforts. This gap is highlighted by a meta-analysis on meat reduction strategies that found huge differences in effect sizes between real-life studies (odds ratio=1.82) and studies on consumers' self-reports (odds ratio=4.2) and intentions (odds ratio=4.14). Due to this huge heterogeneity the authors recommend to prioritizing using observed behavioral changes in future studies (Chang et al. 2023).

Recently, an increasing number of researchers have been investigating strategies to promote behavior change towards reduced meat consumption in response to urgent global challenges like climate change and biodiversity loss. A systematic literature review conducted by Kwasny et al. (2022) provides strong evidence for the impact of interventions on attitudes and intentions related to meat consumption, although limited evidence was found for actual behavior change. Among a broad range of interventions the review investigates the effectiveness of only two specific nudging intervention: making vegetarian food more visible (evidence for high efficacy) and making vegetarian options the default choice (low evidence given) (Kwasny et al., 2022). A second literature review by Taufik et al. (2019) focuses on the effectiveness in targeting different determinants of real-life behavioral interventions implemented in home, retail, and food service settings. However, the review did not provide information regarding the effectiveness of different interventions regarding the promotion of plant-based or reduction of animal-based diets.

A third review by Stiles et al. (2022) focused more specifically on foodservice settings but compared to our study it included also online food service settings and the redesign of products and services. They found that the most promising strategies are menu redesign, followed by menu labelling (Stiles et al., 2022).

We found only one meta-analysis examining strategies (including nudging) to reduce meat consumption (Chang et al., 2023). It focuses only on college/university settings and found a medium mean standardized effect size (odds ratio) of 2.88. In using only observational behavioral studies, they found a medium effect size with choice architecture/nudging interventions in the retail environment being more effective (odds ratio = 1.82) than interventions targeting conscious decision-making processes (odds ratio = 1.68).

While several systematic reviews on the effectiveness of interventions to reduce meat consumption exist, only some include single nudging techniques, no comprehensive review or meta-analysis has specifically tested the efficacy of several nudging techniques alone. The reviews and meta-analysis discussed also incorporate other measures such as financial incentives, meat taxes, mandatory vegetarian days, and educational interventions, which do not involve nudging techniques. Hence, we conclude that there is limited understanding on the overall effectiveness of different nudging interventions in food service settings and the specific conditions in which nudges may effectively facilitate a reduction in meat consumption.

2. Objectives and Research Questions

The overall objective of this study is to systematically identify and synthesize findings from field studies on the effect of different nudging interventions aimed at reducing meat consumption in food service. The following research questions will be addressed:

1. How many field studies on nudging interventions to reduce meat consumption in food service do exist, and what are the characteristics of these studies in terms of
 - a. study country and study year,
 - b. food service settings (e.g., restaurants, canteens) and meal-times (breakfast, lunch, dinner, snack),
 - c. nudging categories (decision information, decision structure and decision assistance) and nudging techniques (translate information, make information visible, provide social reference points, change choice defaults, change option related effort, change range or composition of options, change option consequences, provide reminders, facilitate commitment),
 - d. menu-design (was the nudge implemented in the menu?),
 - e. information to support the effectiveness of the nudge (desk, table, verbal prompt),
 - f. target population (e.g., students, adolescents, general population) and socio-demographics (education, gender, diet habits)?
2. What is the average effect of the nudging interventions to reduce meat consumption and how homogeneous are these effects?
3. In case of heterogeneous effects:
 - a. Does the effectiveness of nudging interventions differ between nudging categories (decision information, decision structure and decision assistance)?
 - b. Do nudging techniques (translate information, make information visible, provide social reference points, change choice defaults, change option related effort, change range or composition of options, change option consequences, provide reminders, facilitate commitment) differ in their effectiveness?
 - c. Are specific food service settings (e.g., restaurants, canteens) and mealtimes (breakfast, lunch, dinner, snack) more receptive for nudging?
 - d. Is the effectiveness of nudging interventions dependent on the target population (e.g. students, adolescents, general population) and socio-demographics (education, gender, diet habits)?
 - e. Is the effectiveness of the nudging intervention influenced by the experimental design? (e.g., length of the experiment, share of vegetarian/vegan dishes in the control and intervention period)

Based on a comprehensive literature search, this analysis offers insights into the effectiveness of nudging interventions and sheds light on possible supporting and limiting factors. Thereby, it provides an evidence-based assistance in the choice of nudges for policy makers, researchers and practitioners.

4. Methods

This protocol was created according to the PRISMA-P guidelines (Shamseer et al., 2015).

Eligibility Criteria

Eligible criteria are set up by the use of PICO-S (Amir-Behghadami & Janati, 2020):

Persons: people eating out-of-home (restaurants, canteens, cafeterias)

Interventions: nudging interventions that aim to reduce meat consumption (fish not included) in food service/out-of-home sector

Control conditions: pre-post designs

Outcomes: %-change in meat consumption (without fish)

Study design: real-life/field experiment, framed field studies

We only include peer-reviewed studies that test a nudge intervention consistent with the definition of Thaler and Sunstein (2009) and assignable to the taxonomy of Münscher et al. (2016, see Table 1). This means that economic incentives and educational measures are not included. We consider all nudging interventions that focus either on meat reduction or the promotion of vegan or vegetarian food. However, we only include studies that allow us to calculate the number of meat dishes ordered in the control and the intervention group because the outcome variable is the %-change in meat consumption.

The nudging interventions must be tested either in a field experiment within a food service setting or in a framed field study that mimic a food service context. Food service in our study refers to “facilities that serve meals and snacks for immediate consumption on site (food away from home)” (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2022) such as restaurants, canteens or cafeterias. Framed field studies encompass controlled environments, such as university gastronomy laboratories, sensory evaluation rooms, or living labs, in which participants make authentic choices and are served with actual meals that they consume.

Study identification, study selection and data collection process

In preparation of the study identification phase, we conducted a broad search with google scholar using the search terms “Nudging”, “Field Study” and “Meat” to identify key articles regarding the different nudging techniques described. Afterwards, a forward search starting from seminal papers in the field was conducted. Within this search process, we realized that different strategies and interventions tested to reduce meat consumption which could be identified as nudging according to our definition, did not necessarily link the intervention to the nudging concept but to behavioral interventions in general or labelling and information provision theories. In order to capture all interventions that classify as “Nudge” according to our definition, we do not include the specific term in the proceeding keyword search.

Key word searches in the following databases are conducted to cover relevant scientific articles from different disciplines (economics, social sciences, psychology and public health): Web of Science, Scopus, PubMed, ProQuest, Medline, PSYNDEX, PubPsych, PsycIn. The search strings for all databases consist of three search components, the first one covers the desired type of study, i.e. (framed) field studies, the second one the food service context, and the third accounts for the outcome variable, i.e. meat reduction or the promotion of vegetarian/vegan/plant-based food. Because of the above mentioned reasons, we

decided to not include a fourth search term to restrict for specific intervention strategies. The search is conducted without imposing any restrictions on date or language; however, due to resource constraints, only studies conducted in English, Italian, and German are included.

For example, the following search term is applied in the database Web of Science:

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(TS=(( field-study OR field-experiment OR field-trial OR real-life-experiment OR real-life-setting OR real-life-study OR natural-experiment OR quasi-experiment* OR real-world-setting OR real-world-study OR living-lab*) AND (restaurant OR canteen OR cafeteria OR cafe OR hotel OR dining OR lunch OR dinner OR breakfast OR buffet OR food-service OR out-of-home OR catering) AND (meat OR vegetarian OR vegan OR plant-based)) )
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Moreover, we also check the reference lists of systematic reviews (Kwasny et al., 2022; Stiles et al., 2022; Taufik et al., 2019) and one meta-analysis (Chang et al., 2023) which focus on meat reduction strategies.

The results produced from the different search strategies (databases, forward search, review screening) are imported into a designated Mendeley folder. The naming convention of this folder maps the funnel structure of the PRISMA flowchart. Example: (# of step in the PRIMSA flowchart)_(Source)

"1_Web of Science" would carry all hits produced by Web of Science (only)

"1_Scopus" would carry all hits in Scopus (only)

Upon completion of the database search, all entries from the level 1 folders are copied into a unified folder, facilitating the elimination of duplicate entries.

All records advanced from literature search will be copied into a separate folder along with the full text pdfs to perform the full text reviews. The pre-defined eligibility criteria will be used to select studies for inclusion in the review. Two independent reviewers will select eligible studies to reduce the risk of mistakes and personal biases. When discrepancies arise, the studies will be thoroughly examined and discussed until a consensus is reached.

5. Data collection process

The screening and coding process will be carried out by all authors, supported by student assistants. In order to reduce bias and errors, eligibility screening (of full papers) and coding will be performed by at least two persons per paper. The coding scheme was developed based on the PsychOpen CAMA template (Burgard et al., 2022) and can be found in the Electronic Appendix.

6. Data Items

We will extract details on the report level (author, year), study level (country, year, availability of socio-demographics, mealtime the experiment targets, menu design, information to support the effectiveness of the nudge given at the table or at the desk, verbal prompt), sample level (age, education, gender, eating habits, setting) and outcome level (nudge category, nudge technique, how many days the experiment lasted, share of vegetarian and vegan dishes in the control and intervention period, number of dishes (meat, fish, vegetarian and vegan) served in the control and intervention period, number of meat dishes (fish not included) in the control and intervention period).

7. Outcomes and prioritization

The outcome measure we use is the risk difference based on the share of dishes served with/without meat (excluding fish) between two measurement points (with nudging intervention versus without nudging interventions). Technically, we use the RD measure in the R package metafor (Viechtbauer, 2010).

8. Risk of bias in individual studies

All papers selected for inclusion in the systematic review will be evaluated by two independent researchers. We use the checklist for quasi-experimental studies (non-randomized Experimental Studies) of JBI (Tufanaru et al., 2020). This tool uses nine criteria to judge on the risk of bias. These criteria will be used as moderators in the meta-analysis, exploring if and to what extent the degree of risk of bias is associated with the effectiveness of nudging interventions.

9. Data synthesis

A random-effects model will be used to fit the data. The amount of heterogeneity (i.e., τ^2), will be estimated using the restricted maximum-likelihood estimator (Viechtbauer, 2005). In addition to the estimate of τ^2 , the Q -test for heterogeneity (Cochran, 1954) and the I^2 statistic (Higgins & Thompson, 2002) will be reported. Studentized residuals and Cook's distances are used to (Viechtbauer & Cheung, 2010) examine whether studies may be outliers and/or influential in the context of the model. Studies with a studentized residual larger than the $100 \times (1 - 0.05/(2 \times k))$ th percentile of a standard normal distribution are considered potential outliers (i.e., using a Bonferroni correction with two-sided $\alpha = 0.05$ for k studies included in the meta-analysis). Studies with a Cook's distance larger than the median plus six times the interquartile range of the Cook's distances will be considered to be influential. The rank correlation test (Begg & Mazumdar, 1994) and the regression test (Sterne & Egger, 2005), using the standard error of the observed outcomes as predictor, will be used to check for funnel plot asymmetry. Moderator analysis will be performed via meta-regression. In case of dependencies among effect sizes, multilevel meta-analysis will be used. The analysis will be carried out using R (version 4.3.0) and the metafor package (version 4.0.0) (Viechtbauer, 2010).

10. Meta-bias(es)

We will explore the funnel plot for asymmetry, perform Egger's regression test and perform the usual influence diagnostics as implemented in the influence() function of the R package metafor (Viechtbauer, 2010). Depending on the presence of potential biases, sensitivity analyses will be performed.

11. Confidence in cumulative evidence

The strength of the body of evidence will be assessed though taking into account the following criteria:

- Use of a Random effects model: The use of a random effects model in the analysis helps to account for potential heterogeneity across studies and enhances the generalizability of the findings.
- Prediction interval of summary effect does not contain zero: The prediction interval is a measure of uncertainty around the estimated summary effect. If the prediction interval does not include zero, it suggests a significant effect and increases the confidence in the findings.

- Quality of evidence (as operationalized by the JBI instrument (Tufanaru et al., 2020). The degree to which effect sizes are associated with primary study quality will be assessed.
- Meta-bias refers to the potential biases that can arise from the selection, inclusion, or publication of studies in a meta-analysis. A thorough assessment of potential biases will be conducted, reported and discussed.

By considering these criteria, the strength of the body of evidence will be evaluated, providing a reliable and comprehensive assessment of the findings.

Contributions

IS drafted the original manuscript and developed the conceptual framework. MB developed the methodological and analytical parts, and revised the entire manuscript. GG and GS provided feedback on the conceptual and theoretical part. All authors approved the final version of the manuscript.

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